

CHARACTERISTICS OF LEARNING RUSSIAN LANGUAGE STYLISTICS IN NON-PHILOLOGICAL TECHNICAL INSTITUTES OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract:

The article describes the role of dialogues and role plays in teaching grammar and developing speaking skills, critical thinking of students in the lessons. As we know role plays may also include plays, dramas, sociodramas, and simulation. Here we use the general term role play for all of these types of activities, but we will also discuss the specific definitions, benefits, and uses of plays, dramas and sociodramas, and simulation in this section.

Key Words: plays, dramas and sociodramas, and simulation drills and dialogues, interactive methods, learn, analyze, role-play, drama, movies, cartoons and pictures, independent, types of activities, benefits of Role Play
Characteristics of Learning Russian Language Stylistics in Non-Philological Technical Institutes of Uzbekistan:

The Russian language, as a means of inter-ethnic communication in Uzbekistan, occupies one of the leading positions. Bilingualism in Uzbek-Russian society plays a positive role in the learning process of the Russian language by students with an Uzbek-speaking background. In the conditions of scientific and technical progress of our society the formation of a highly qualified specialist, whose speech meets the standards accepted in the educated environment, which are notable for their expressiveness, beauty and accuracy, acquires a great role. Language as the main means of human communication is arranged in such a way as to perform various functions adequately to the intentions and desires of an individual linguistic personality and the objectives of the human community, while the functions of language are understood to mean the use of potential means of language in speech for different purposes.

It is known that language in general is intended for realization of people's communication in the most various situations of human activity, i.e., the main function of language is the function of communication (communicative function), consisting in mutual exchange of statements by members of the language collective. And if language is a tool (means) of communication, then speech is a way of communication produced by this tool, which is distinguished by its specificity and uniqueness, aspiration to a certain goal, determined by the situation of communication. Speech is a kind of free creative activity of a person. And a person who speaks literary language has a whole set of variants at his disposal, each of which is intended for use in a certain sphere of life. And in this ability to choose the appropriate variant of literary language is the ability to speak the language.

At the same time, it should be noted that speech is considered good if it meets the three most general criteria: correctness, accuracy, aesthetics. In my opinion, the correct use of the Russian language in various spheres of communication helps students to develop these qualities. Therefore, the task of a Russian language teacher in a non-linguistic technical university is to teach students to perform actions that lead to the formation of speech skills and abilities necessary in the educational, scientific, industrial and other spheres of life. Since each functional style of the Russian language is a subsystem, which is determined by the conditions and objectives of communication in all spheres of social activity, in the technical university at classes in the Russian language for students of the state language of instruction (Uzbek), much attention is paid to the study of the features of each style separately, namely: scientific, official - business, publicist, artistic and conversational everyday life. Of course, when studying stylistics, it is necessary to take into account that the object of study is students of non-language, in particular, technical profile with the state (Uzbek) language of instruction. Therefore, the preference is still given to the study of scientific, official business and journalistic styles.

Knowledge of stylistic features of scientific style (accuracy, abstraction, logicity and objectivity of presentation, use of special scientific vocabulary and terms), linguistic peculiarities of scientific language are necessary for students in the educational process for writing such scientific works as: scientific article, report, course project, essay, diploma thesis, etc. Also, when studying the scientific style of students should learn to compress scientific material, to create on the basis of compression such secondary texts as: abstract, review, scientific review, essay, essay, essay. Undoubtedly, the creation of such texts requires a lot of work on the part of the teacher, careful thought out methods, timely control, training exercises. The study of the scientific style is based on various manuals developed by teachers of higher education institutions in Uzbekistan.

Thus, for example, in T.T.Keldiev's textbook "Russian language" the study of the science language is based on the text material. The purpose of the textbook is to help students of non-philological universities to master syntactic constructions of the Russian language, expressing certain semantic relations, and to develop skills of using syntactic constructions in monological speech. The manual uses texts of the general scientific plan "Science and society", "The Great Silk Road", "The quality of a true scientist", "Nature conservation and ecology", etc.

Various tasks are attached to the texts: pretext, textual and posttextual tasks. Our teachers of Russian language on the basis of pretext tasks carry out a huge work to prepare students for the perception of the text: dictionary work, work on spelling words, on the formulation of phrases and sentences. This is followed by the text work: introductory conversation, reading the text. After reading the text, students work on the content of the text, answering questions, highlighting the main information and secondary.

The following are practical tasks, such as: finding the general vocabulary and terms, finishing sentences, writing down complex sentences, etc. The manual also contains samples of secondary texts and language formulas (cliches), on the basis of which students learn to make their own abstracts, essays, reviews, reviews. to motivate the educational and cognitive activities of students annually by teachers of Russian language of the Bukhara branch of the Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and AgriculturalMechanization Engineers of held an exhibition of essays, which is attended by all first-year students. The best works are displayed on the stand and then published.

For students, it is a good incentive that allows us to involve them in research work. Understanding the importance of the scientific style in the educational process, it is necessary to take into account the need to know the rules of writing official papers and documents in modern society.

Therefore, when studying the Russian language, we pay great attention to the study of the official business style, its lexical, morphological, syntactic features, the preparation of business documents and letters. At the same time, students learn how to prepare personal and service documents (resumes, autobiographies, testimonials, statements, receipts, reports, minutes, reports, explanatory notes, references, etc.), knowing that they need to submit the entire package of documents after graduation.

As Jumayeva Shahlo Shokirovna said, teaching children is a challenge. They are fidget. They like to play. Let them play though they are students. Let them be children as even teacher is a child in the heart. Students are also interested in the study of the journalistic style. In the classes on this style students are taught to express their thoughts in a competent and consistent way while preparing their public speeches on free topics. They form communicative skills and abilities in the aspect of public speaking:

- independently prepare adequate communication tasks of visual materials and use them competently;
- use logical and feedback techniques in their speech;
- independently define the goals and target audience for communication based on the purpose of the activity.

The purpose of such presentations is to convince the audience of the importance and fairness of the situation. And only those who speak warmly, vividly, expressively, intelligently and, finally, convincingly, can be involved. The purpose of such presentations is to convince the audience of the importance and fairness of the situation. And only those who speak warmly, brightly, expressively, intelligently and, finally, convincingly, can be fascinated. Let's give an approximate subject of public speeches for students:

- Humane person. What is he like?
- Etiquette in our lives.
- A man without a homeland as a nightingale without a song.
- Without history there is no future.
- What is a personality?
- Modern entrepreneur, what is he like?

The topics of speeches can be different, the most important thing it should be actual and interesting for students. In our opinion, the oratory skills acquired during the classes will be useful for students both in defending their coursework and diploma projects, and in further professional activities. It should be noted that the study of Russian language stylistics is dictated by the fact that such speech and stylistic mistakes are often made:

- violation of speech etiquette rules;
- unjustified mixing of styles;
- abuse of foreign words and stylistic turns of other languages (barbarism);
- poor style;
- banality of style.

In this regard, the modern Russian language of Uzbeks is developing at a dynamic pace. The sphere of use is quite wide. It is actively used in science, journalism and in the official environment. As President of our state Sh. Mirziyoyev noted, "The great Russian culture has always been and will always be an integral part of the spiritual life of Uzbek society. He also said that Uzbekistan will publish a 100-volume collection of "Masterpieces

of Russian Classics" in the Uzbek language. He also noted that our country's plans include intensive study of the Russian language and propaganda of Russian-language books.

Uzbekistan and the Russian Federation have agreed to promote scientific, educational and humanitarian programmes and exchanges to the maximum extent possible, using the Russian language in the interests of political, scientific, spiritual and economic consolidation of Uzbekistan and Russia. In Uzbekistan, the Russian language is largely dependent on ethnolinguistic contacts. Thus, we come to the conclusion that stylistics is not only one of the most important sections of the Russian language, but also a necessary component of the entire educational process in a technical university.

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